

ELIXIR-STEERS WP₂ Activities and Outputs: Dissemination Package

ELIXIR-STEERS WP₂: Implementation of research software best practices through ELIXIR Communities

WP₂ aims to develop and promote a practical collection of best practices and indicators for research software and workflows across ELIXIR. The work has been carried forward through close engagement with ELIXIR Communities and Nodes - including monthly presentations, Communities use cases, workshops, hackathons, webinars - to test, refine and disseminate guidance in real settings.

Objectives:

- O2.1 / Task 2.1 – Building the technical toolkit for software best practices
WP₂ develops a practical toolkit of best practices for research software and workflows in the life sciences. This includes work on software quality, sustainability, reproducibility, software management plans, benchmarking and guidance for emerging areas such as AI and ML.
- O2.2 / Task 2.2 – Identifying efficiency indicators for research software and workflows
WP₂ defines indicators that help assess the quality, efficiency, sustainability and scientific impact of research software quality and workflows. These indicators support benchmarking, help communities evaluate software more systematically, and provide an evidence base for improving tools and practices.
- O2.3 / Task 2.3 – Assessment and dissemination through Community engagement
WP₂ works with ELIXIR Nodes and ELIXIR Communities to review, test and refine best practices and indicators through real use cases. This task also supports uptake through meetings, hackathons, shared examples and dissemination activities across ELIXIR and beyond.

Start here – how to use this package

Depending on your interest, you can:

Explore existing resources

Browse webinar recordings and WP2 outputs to discover available outputs, services and best practices.

Identify relevant material

Check the mapped content and toolkit structure to see where your work, tools or use cases could contribute.

Get involved in D2.2

Contribute by sharing existing materials, examples, or by co-developing or advising on specific sections of the toolkit.

Disseminate within your network

Reuse this package or selected materials to raise awareness and stimulate discussion in your Node, Platform or Community.

Publicly Available Materials and Outputs

These resources can support ELIXIR Nodes, Platforms and Communities in improving software quality, increasing visibility of their tools, and aligning with emerging best practices in research software.

Milestones

- [ELIXIR-STEERS M2.1: Community engagement scoreboard created](#)
- [ELIXIR-STEERS Milestone report: M2.2 Collection of existing best-practices and indicators for research software](#)
- [ELIXIR-STEERS M2.3: Delivery of a Hackathon engaging three or more nominated ELIXIR Communities](#)
- [ELIXIR-STEERS M2.4: Community engagement scoreboard updated](#)
- M2.5: Delivery of a Hackathon engaging additional Communities for outreach (*due M30*)

Deliverables

- [ELIXIR-STEERS D2.1 Report on best-practices and indicators available and used by selected Communities](#)
- D2.2: Research software and workflows best-practice toolkit (*due M36*)

WP2 also led the first ELIXIR-STEERS policy brief, focused on strategies to strengthen the credit and recognition of non-traditional research artefacts in research assessment. The brief promotes a more inclusive and sustainable framework for recognising outputs such as datasets, software, workflows and training materials, drawing on ELIXIR life science examples while remaining applicable across research domains. The policy brief is available here:

[ELIXIR-STEERS D1.9 Strategies for enhancing the credit and recognition of research artefacts](#)

Internal Working Materials

Community Engagement Scoreboards: Infrastructure Components and RSQ Indicators Uptake inside ELIXIR Communities

The Community Engagement Scoreboards are internal working documents used by WP2 to track changes in Community engagement, service uptake and awareness of RSQ indicators throughout the project. Building on the first version created in M2.1 and the updated version prepared for M2.4, they support a structured assessment of how ELIXIR Communities engage with STEERS, use infrastructure components, and adopt research software best practices, while also informing follow-up actions.

- WP2 M2.1: Community Engagement Scoreboard
- WP2 M2.4: Community Engagement Scoreboard updated

Webinars on Underused Infrastructure Components

WP2 also organised a dedicated webinar series showcasing a set of underused infrastructure components identified through the M2.1 Community Engagement Scoreboard, with the aim of increasing awareness, understanding and uptake across ELIXIR Communities. The featured services included BIP! Scholar, APICURON, DOME Registry, ProTES, Software Management Wizard and OpenEBench. Recordings of the webinars are available here:

- ELIXIR-STEERS WP2 webinar on underused infrastructure components (October 2025)
- ELIXIR-STEERS WP2 webinar on underused infrastructure components (November 2...

Current Development of Deliverable D2.2

Deliverable D2.2, Research Software and Workflows Best-Practice Toolkit, is under active development within WP2. A draft structure is in place and is being iteratively refined through partner contributions and alignment with ELIXIR Communities, Platforms and Nodes. This work is closely linked to the [RSQKit](#) (from EOSC EVERSE): through STEERS contentathons and hackathons, WP2 has developed STEERS-related material for RSQKit, with outputs being translated into new RSQKit pages. A link to the working document is provided below:

- D2.2 Research software and workflows best-practice toolkit

Contributions to D2.2 can include:

- sharing existing tools, workflows or practices
- contributing examples or use cases
- co-developing or advising on specific sections

STEERS WP2 Workshops and Hackathons

STEERS WP2 has contributed to a series of hands-on workshops and hackathons with EOSC EVERSE to support the development of Research Software Stories and RSQKit content. These activities provide practical opportunities for participants to document tools, services, workflows and best practices in a reusable format, while also feeding into the development of D2.2.

- [WP2/WP3 STEERS Workshop, December 2025](#) – contentation activities supporting RSQKit and STEERS-related research software quality content.
- [Research Software Stories event, Amsterdam, April 2026](#) – hands-on drafting of Research Software Stories.
- [ELIXIR All-Hands co-located hackathon, 11 June 2026 10:00-12:30 CEST, Lyon and online](#) – the final event in this series, introducing Research Software Stories as part of RSQKit and supporting participants to start drafting one.
 - An optional online introductory session will take place on 1 June 2026, 10:00-11:00 CEST.

Please sign up here: [📄 Research Software Stories Hackathons - Sign-up sheet](#)

More information:

[📄 Second STEERS/EVERSE hackathon: drafting Research Software Stories](#)

[📄 M2.5: Delivery of a Hackathon engaging additional Communities for outreach](#)

Recommended Dissemination Actions

To support the uptake and wider dissemination of ELIXIR-STEERS WP2 activities and outputs, we invite ELIXIR Nodes, Platforms and Communities to share the materials included in this package within their networks.

Suggested Email / Slack Template

Subject: ELIXIR-STEERS WP2 resources on research software quality

Email body:

Please find below a dissemination package with resources developed within ELIXIR-STEERS WP2, focusing on research software best practices, quality indicators, supporting infrastructure, and the recognition of research artefacts.

The package includes links to WP2 outputs, webinar recordings, the Policy Brief "*Strategies for enhancing the credit and recognition of research artefacts*", and the D2.2 best-practice toolkit currently under development.

We encourage you to explore the materials and identify where your Node, Platform or Community could benefit from or contribute to the D2.2 toolkit. Contributions will help ensure that the toolkit reflects the diversity of practices across ELIXIR Nodes, Platforms and Communities.

For further information or to discuss potential contributions, please contact Federica Quaglia: federica.quaglia8@gmail.com/ federica.quaglia@unipd.it

Expected actions

We encourage recipients to:

- Engage with the materials to increase awareness of research software best practices
- Identify opportunities for contribution to the D2.2 toolkit
- Promote and discuss the resources and the policy brief within their networks
- Reach out for discussion and collaboration on WP2 activities

Further Information and Contact

For further information about WP2 activities and dissemination materials, please contact:

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WP2 is co-led by:

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- Fotis Psomopoulos (CERTH).